

Synthesis of some 1-Substituted-3-methyl-5-(2',4',6'-trimethoxyphenyl)-4-(N¹-substituted-*p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrazoles as Potential Antifungal and Antibacterial Agents

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Coupling of 1-methyl-3-(2',4',6'-trimethoxyphenyl)propan-1,3-dione (1) with different diazotised sulphonamide bases gives the corresponding 1-methyl-3-(2',4',6'-trimethoxyphenyl)-2-(N¹-substituted-*p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)propan-1,3-diones (2a-1). Subsequent cyclisation with substituted hydrazines yields the pyrazole derivatives 3a-f, 3k, 3l and 4a-j. The antifungal and antibacterial activities of these compounds have been evaluated and some of them were found to exhibit considerable activity.

PYRAZOLES and especially arylazopyrazoles are found to possess antidiuretic¹, antianthelmintic² and hypoglycaemic³ activities in addition to fungicidal activity^{4,5}. Pyrazoles having sulphonamide moiety attached through an azo-linkage have been reported to exhibit antibacterial activity of varying degree⁶⁻⁸. In the present communication, we report the synthesis of some 1-substituted-3-methyl-5-(2',4',6'-trimethoxyphenyl)-4-(N¹-substituted-*p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrazoles (3a-f, 3k, 3l and 4a-j).

1-Methyl-3-(2',4',6'-trimethoxyphenyl)propan-1,3-dione⁹ (1) was coupled with diazotised solution of the appropriate sulphonamide bases to give coupled β-diketones (2a-1).

Further, these coupled β-diketones were cyclised with two different hydrazines, viz. 4-methylphenylhydrazine hydrochloride and 4-methylphenylsulphonylhydrazine to give 1-(4''-methylphenyl)-3-methyl-5-(2',4',6'-trimethoxyphenyl)-4-(N¹-substituted-*p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrazole (3a-f, k, l) and

1-(4''-methylphenylsulphonyl) 3-methyl-5-(2',4',6'-trimethoxyphenyl)-4-(N¹-substituted-*p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrazole (4a-j) derivatives.

Biological testing: All the pyrazoles synthesised were screened *in vitro* against bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* at 10 and 20 μg ml⁻¹ concentrations using cup-plate agar diffusion method¹⁰. The compounds showed marginal activity at 10 μg ml⁻¹ concentration and better inhibition at 20 μg ml⁻¹. The derivatives 3k and 4h were found to be most active against *E. coli* while 4f was active against *S. aureus*. Compounds were also screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Cryosporum panorum* at 20 μg ml⁻¹ concentration using Czapek-Dox nutrient medium¹¹. Compounds 3k (85.4%) and 4i (97.55%) showed maximum inhibition against *A. flavus* while 4g showed 81.3% inhibition against *A. fumigatus*, which are comparable to that of a standard compound Bavistein showing 100% inhibition during the experiments.

Experimental

Procedure for the typical case has been described. Melting points were taken in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Pmr spectra were recorded on a JEOL JNM-FX 200 FT (199.50 MHz) spectrometer.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 1-METHYL-3-(2',4',6'-TRIMETHOXYPHENYL)-2-(N¹-SUBSTITUTED-*p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO)PROPAN-1,3-DIONE (2a - b)

Compd. no.	R	M p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
					C	H	N	S
2a	Pyrimidin-2-yl	225-27	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₇ N ₅ S	54.1 (53.80)	4.41 (4.48)	13.81 (13.64)	6.31 (6.23)
2b	4,6-Dimethoxypyrimidin-2-yl	190-91	84	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₉ N ₅ S	52.61 (52.35)	4.68 (4.71)	12.25 (12.21)	5.44 (5.58)
2c	3-Methyl-1,2,4-thiadiazol-5-yl	195-97	85	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₇ N ₅ S ₂	49.59 (49.53)	4.23 (4.31)	13.30 (13.13)	12.11 (12.00)
2d	2-Methoxyphenyl	190-92	80	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ O ₉ N ₅ S	57.89 (57.61)	4.97 (4.99)	7.78 (7.76)	5.85 (5.91)
2e	Phenyl	187-89	82	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₇ N ₅ S	58.88 (58.70)	4.68 (4.89)	8.22 (8.21)	6.40 (6.26)
2f	2-Methylphenyl	176-78	80	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₅ S	59.48 (59.42)	5.08 (5.14)	8.12 (8.00)	6.36 (6.09)
2g	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-4-yl	180-82	78	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₅ S	55.80 (55.42)	4.88 (4.99)	12.91 (12.93)	5.84 (5.91)
2h	3-Methylphenyl	195-97	80	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₅ S	59.48 (59.42)	5.08 (5.14)	8.11 (8.00)	6.13 (6.09)
2i	4-Methylphenyl	186-87	78	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₅ S	59.49 (59.42)	5.08 (5.14)	8.22 (8.00)	6.15 (6.09)
2j	H	138-40	75	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₇ N ₅ S	52.61 (52.41)	4.79 (4.82)	9.58 (9.65)	7.31 (7.35)
2k	4-Methylpyrimidin-2-yl	158-60	82	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₇ N ₅ S	54.51 (54.64)	4.49 (4.74)	13.36 (13.28)	6.11 (6.07)
2l	4-Chlorophenyl	158-60	80	CHONSCI	54.98 (54.89)	4.47 (4.57)	7.60 (7.68)	5.76 (5.86)

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 1-(4'''-METHYLPHENYL)-3-METHYL-5-(2',4',6'-TRIMETHOXYPHENYL)-4-(N¹-SUBSTITUTED-*p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO)PYRAZOLES (3a - h, k, l) AND 1-(4'''-METHYLPHENYL-SULPHONYL)-3-METHYL-5-(2',4',6'-TRIMETHOXYPHENYL)-4-(N¹-SUBSTITUTED-*p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO)PYRAZOLES (4a - j)*

Compd. no.	M p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	S
3a	234-35	78	C ₂₀ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₇ S	60.21 (60.10)	4.80 (4.84)	16.45 (16.36)	5.42 (5.34)
3b	187-89	80	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₇ N ₇ S	58.32 (58.27)	4.98 (5.00)	14.91 (14.87)	4.68 (4.85)
3c	175-76	75	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₇ S	56.31 (56.21)	4.62 (4.68)	15.88 (15.83)	5.23 (5.16)
3d	208-09	70	C ₃₃ H ₃₃ O ₈ N ₅ S	63.28 (63.15)	5.02 (5.26)	11.31 (11.16)	5.14 (5.10)
3e	173-74	75	C ₃₂ H ₃₁ O ₆ N ₅ S	64.41 (64.81)	5.18 (5.49)	11.68 (11.72)	5.42 (5.36)
3f	176-78	72	C ₃₃ H ₃₃ O ₇ N ₅ S	64.88 (64.81)	5.39 (5.40)	11.55 (11.45)	5.28 (5.23)
3g	162-64	72	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₅ N ₇ S	61.31 (62.24)	5.20 (5.26)	15.51 (15.62)	5.11 (5.10)
3h	138-40	72	C ₃₃ H ₃₃ O ₆ N ₅ S	64.48 (64.10)	5.45 (5.50)	11.75 (11.68)	5.36 (5.34)
3k	128-29	80	C ₃₁ H ₃₁ O ₅ N ₇ S	60.77 (60.68)	5.02 (5.05)	15.89 (15.98)	5.13 (5.22)
3l	158-60	74	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ O ₆ N ₅ SCI	60.88 (60.80)	4.68 (4.75)	11.18 (11.08)	5.16 (5.06)
4a	181-83	70	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₇ S ₂	54.34 (54.29)	4.33 (4.37)	14.80 (14.78)	9.72 (9.65)
4b	114-16	70	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₉ N ₅ S ₂	53.20 (53.11)	4.45 (4.56)	13.48 (13.55)	8.78 (8.85)
4c	103-105	68	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ C ₇ N ₇ S ₂	51.02 (50.95)	4.14 (4.24)	14.38 (14.34)	14.14 (14.05)
4d	119-20	71	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	57.38 (57.30)	4.62 (4.77)	10.23 (10.13)	9.11 (9.26)
4e	121-23	78	C ₃₂ H ₃₁ O ₇ N ₅ S ₂	58.18 (58.09)	4.60 (4.68)	10.51 (10.59)	9.62 (9.68)
4f	108-10	70	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₇ N ₅ S ₂	58.71 (58.66)	4.84 (4.88)	10.44 (10.37)	9.54 (9.48)
4g	124-26	71	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₇ N ₇ S ₂	55.63 (55.57)	4.72 (4.77)	14.25 (14.18)	9.24 (9.26)
4h	109-10	70	C ₃₃ H ₃₃ O ₇ N ₅ S ₂	58.69 (58.66)	4.84 (4.88)	10.36 (10.37)	9.53 (9.48)
4i	101-103	68	C ₃₂ H ₃₃ O ₇ N ₅ S ₂	58.72 (58.66)	4.78 (4.88)	10.42 (10.37)	9.51 (9.48)
4j	147-49	68	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₅ S ₂	53.38 (53.33)	4.72 (4.61)	11.86 (11.96)	11.00 (10.94)

*All the compounds gave satisfactory pmr data.

1-Methyl-3-(2',4',6'-trimethoxyphenyl)-2-(N¹-pyrimidin-2''-yl-p-sulphamylbenzeneazo)propan-1,3-dione (2a). *General procedure:* To an ice-cold solution of the β -diketone (**1**; 0.002 mol) in ethylalcohol (30 ml) containing sodium acetate (10 g) was added gradually a diazotised solution of *N*¹-pyrimidin-2-yl sulphanylamine (0.002 mol) during stirring which was further continued for 5 min. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and left overnight. The coloured solid which separated out was filtered, washed well with water and dried. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid—ethanol to give **2a** as a yellow solid.

1-(4'''-Methylphenyl)-3-methyl-5-(2',4',6'-trimethoxyphenyl)-4-(N¹-pyrimidin-2''-yl-p-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrazole (3a). *General procedure:* To a solution of **2a** (0.001 mol) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was added a solution of 4-methylphenylhydrazine hydrochloride (0.001 mol) fused with sodium acetate (0.5 g) in glacial acetic acid. The mixture was refluxed in an oil-bath for 16 h. Water was added to the reaction mixture when an orange solid separated out. It was filtered, dried and purified by passing through a column of silica gel and eluting with benzene—acetone (4 : 1) to give **3a** as an orange solid; δ (DMSO-*d*₆+CDCl₃, 4 : 1) 2.29 (3H, s, CH₃ at C-4'''), 2.52 (3H, s, CH₃ at C-3), 3.48 (6H, s, 2×OCH₃ at C-2' and C-6'), 3.79 (3H, s, OCH₃ at C-4'), 6.08 (2H, s, H-3' and H-5'), 6.80 (1H, d, *J* 8Hz, H-5'''), 7.16 (4H, s, H-2''', H-3''', H-5''', H-6'''), 7.54 (d2 H, *J* 8Hz, H-2'' and H-6''), 7.72 (2H, d, *J* 8Hz, H-3'' and H-5'') and 8.01 (2H, d, *J* 8Hz, H-4'' and H-6'').

1-(4'''-Methylphenylsulphonyl)-5-methyl-5-(2',4',6'-trimethoxyphenyl)-4-(N¹-pyrimidin-2''-yl-p-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrazole (4a). *General procedure:* A solution of **2a** (0.001 mol) and 4-methylphenylsulphonylhydrazine (0.001 mol) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) containing two drops of concentrated sulphuric acid was refluxed in an oil-bath for 16 h.

The orange solid which separated out on adding water in excess was filtered, dried and purified by passing through a column of silica gel. Eluting with benzene—acetone (17 : 3) gave **4a** as an orange solid; δ (CD₃COCD₃) 2.26 (3H, s, CH₃ at C-4'''), 2.38 (3H, s, CH₃ at C-3), 3.60 (6H, s, 2×OCH₃ at C-2' and C-6'), 3.78 (3H, s, OCH₃ at C-4'), 6.12 (2H, s, H-3' and H-5'), 6.82 (1H, d, *J* 8Hz, H-5'''), 7.23 (4H, s, H-2''', H-3''', H-5''', H-6'''), 7.27 (2H, d, *J* 8Hz, H-2'' and H-6''), 7.54 (2H, d, *J* 8Hz, H-3'' and H-5'') and 8.00 (2H, d, *J* 8Hz, H-4'' and H-6'').

The characterisation data of various compounds synthesised are given in Tables 1 and 2.

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